

THE IMPORTANCE OF NURSE KNOWLEDGE ON THE QUALITY OF HEALTHCARE DELIVERY

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The Importance of Nurse Knowledge on the Quality of Healthcare Delivery

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Abstract

This study identifies the knowledge, implementation, and evaluation of triage system among healthcare providers on quality healthcare delivery. Mainly, it answers the relationship between knowledge, implementation, evaluation, and quality healthcare delivery among nurses in the triage system. The descriptive-correlational and causal comparative research designs were employed in the study. The study was conducted in Polymedic Medical Plaza, Madonna and Child Hospital, Maria Reyna Xavier University Hospital, Capitol University Medical Center, and JR Borja General Hospital. Likewise, the Nursing Need Theory, Environmental Theory, Deliberative Nursing Process Theory, and Theory of Interpersonal Relations were utilized as the basis of the study. A questionnaire was used as the leading tool in gathering data from the 260 participants. The study identified the participants who are nurses who have a background understanding and experience about triage system. There is a significant relationship between knowledge, implementation, evaluation, and quality healthcare delivery of triage systems. Emergency care is the best predictor of quality healthcare delivery among nurses. EXO-yLobite Triage System Quality Healthcare Delivery Model was developed to explain further that Quality Health Care Delivery is directly mediated by knowledge regarding implementation and evaluation of nurses in the triage system.

Keywords: *knowledge, implementation, evaluation, triage system, and quality healthcare delivery*

Introduction

Understanding

A study by Malak, Al-Faqeer, and Yehia (2022) stated that triage pertains to the process of assessing and classifying the patients who tend to visit the ED or the emergency department. In this way, through the triage system they can cater prioritization to the patients who really need immediate care and treatment that is aligned to the needs of the patients. This is usually done by the nurses in the emergency department, with that, the nurses working in this department must really understand well the purpose and how to properly execute the triage system. This research also revealed that emergency nurses in their research possess enough knowledge of triage and practice well, but their skills are fair.

AlShatarat et al. (2022) stated that it was noted in their study that triage knowledge and practical application among ED nurses working in multinational settings is quite high which translates to better results. Quality enhancement strategies can also help improve triage knowledge and practice. The study also revealed that the majority of them are adequately educated and trained in practice, especially triage knowledge management among the ED nurses, yet still some aspects need to be worked on.

Vujančić et al. (2022) evaluated in their study the differences between patients and nurses on the perception of caring behavior in a health care system. Communication and listening skills are essential for the effective relationship between nurses and patients and for better patient care. When nurses know and understand the needs of the patient, it is not hard for the nurse to give the proper healthcare that the patient needs.

Clinical Judgment

Guerrero (2019) stated in his study that as part of their practice, clinical judgment is about how one can use the knowledge, skills, and competence to make good decisions in order to avert harmful consequences to the patient. Nurses who do not reason clinically may fail to recognize when a patient's condition worsens and make reckless decisions that may result in substandard care. When clinical judgment is exercised properly, patients' safety is enhanced and desired outcomes are attained.

A study by Miller et al. (2019) a good clinical decision or clinical judgment in the practice is multifaceted and entails numerous steps such as processing information, evaluating different forms of evidence, and utilizing appropriate knowledge to determine the most suitable interventions for provision of patient care. It may involve fast judgments and actions. Clinical decision-making or judgment is a continuous process and, in most cases, contextual, and research work is geared towards establishing the best means of making evidence-based decisions in various situations. Dewi et al. (2021) emphasized in their study that critical thinking skills strengthened through nursing rounds, reflective case discussions, will lead to sound decision making in patients' care, hence fewer mistakes. Nursing handover is also important in avoiding unforeseen events and enhances the safety of patients. It can be suggested for the hospital to encourage their nurses to enhance their skills on making sound clinical judgment to deliver a quality healthcare delivery.

Expert Assessment

Wiseman et al. (2023) emphasized in their study the need for thorough evaluation and assessment of patients in minimizing adverse occurrence within any healthcare system. In line to that, according to a study by Kurniawan and Hariyati (2019) there is really a need

for a good patient assessment in nursing practice. It points out that the conduct of accurate and timely assessments is necessary for safeguarding patients and enhancing their treatment outcomes.

A study by Fontenot et al. (2022) stated the significance of physical examination in nursing practice. Physical assessment is limited by time constraints, the culture of the unit, vague accountability, over-dependence on gadgets, and weak self-efficacy towards assessing one's skills.

Ajibade (2023) stated the significance of person-centered care in assessing patients' requirements and in organizing care. It indicates the importance of employing evidence-based nursing techniques and engaging the patient in active decision-making. The research explains the stages of care planning such as identification of needs, choosing interventions, and ordering patient preferences. In addition, it also highlights the need for holistic care that includes all components of the patient's life; physical, psychological, social, and spiritual.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between the knowledge, implementation, and evaluation of the triage system among healthcare providers on quality healthcare delivery. Additionally, the study aimed to develop a structural model that best fit the quality healthcare delivery of the triage system among nurses in the hospital. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the level of knowledge of the triage system among nurses on quality healthcare delivery with regard to:
 - 1.1. understanding;
 - 1.2. clinical judgment; and
 - 1.3. expert assessment?
2. Is there a significant relationship between quality healthcare delivery and their knowledge of the triage system?

Methodology

Research Design

The research used descriptive-correlational and causal-comparative methods of investigation in assessing the relationship between the variables. Descriptive correlational research looks at the relationship between two or more variables without inferring cause and effect, while causal comparative research investigates cause-effect relationship. These relationships can be expressed in causal models that help explain the relationship and its likely occurrence.

According to Stangor (2011), the descriptive correlational method is designed to discover relationships among variables and predict future events from present knowledge. It helps determine if two or more variables are associated with each other by explaining their relationship but not necessarily implying that this relationship is also a cause. Meanwhile, causal comparative research is a type of research method where the researcher tries to find out if there is a causal effect relationship between dependent and independent variables. In other words, the researcher using this method wants to know whether one thing changing affects another thing, and if so, why. The researcher can look at previous events and draw conclusions and cause-and-effect relationships. But of course, there may be sometimes when it is not possible to do so. Then, they can collect information about a group of participants and observe the changes in the long run. (Villegas, 2022).

Respondents

A total of 260 participants from five different hospitals across various patient conditions including those with triage experience in the Emergency department participated in this research where Nurses currently working in the emergency room and other areas were included. Nurses who took part in this survey understand what triage is and so have practiced it. However, with the recent turn of events in 2020, these hospitals devised means to address this emerging challenge. It was deduced that these hospitals were not extremely short of nurses as they decided to mix and randomly select nurses from all departments and assign them a role in triage. Stratified sampling is helpful in representation bias, which is the bias in research that occurs when a subset of a population is excluded from the sample. This improves the external validity of the study and reduces the risk of research biases such as coverage bias. A total of 260 respondents was determined using the Raosoft sample size calculator.

Instrument

The research instrument consisted of a questionnaire adapted from the tools used in the study of Alshatarat et al. (2021), Valdez G. F (2019), and Moon S. et al. (2018) where the questions formulated for this study were extracted, and rephrased suitable even for the participants who are already in a depressing situation, especially to those who are already after their shift. Together with the guidance of the Adviser/Liceo de Cagayan College Dean, application of suggestions and recommendations on the questions to be made fit for the participants. Questions were made shorter and fewer to keep the participants interested in answering the tool. The top part covers the indicators of their level of knowledge and implementation of triage in handling the clients and the next part of the questionnaire covers the indicators of evaluation of the triage system by utilizing a five-point scale from 1 to 5 Likert like type Scale and giving them options to choose as their answer for the questions. This is to measure their response to the given item. Higher scores indicate more

positive knowledge of the triage system on quality health care delivery by the participants. This is the scoring guide with a descriptive rating and qualitative interpretation.

Procedure

After the careful assessment and review of the manuscript for the research, the investigator sought approval from the adviser -- the dean of the Nursing Post-Graduate Studies', the investigator looked for nurses who took part in the research were oriented with the study purpose and were assured that their participation was purely voluntary and that their responses would remain private before consent was obtained from them. Data collection was done in December 2023, using a devised questionnaire administered to nurses of selected hospitals in Cagayan de Oro City. The focus of the questionnaire was the comprehension, utilization and evaluation of triage systems by the healthcare nurses.

The analysis was done using Windows SPSS. The data were encoded in the Windows SPSS database to ensure the quality of all the data entered and for quality control in the data entry process. The data were assessed for completeness, consistency, and missing values. Cronbach's alpha was used to evaluate the internal consistency of the study instrument with the level of significance set at $\alpha = .05$.

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to describe the data. Pearson product moment correlation was used to determine the degree of association between interpersonal skills and independent variables. Multiple regressions were utilized to identify the best predictor for the application of triage system among healthcare providers handling clients.

For the analysis of the data, different statistical approaches were employed. For problems 1, 2, 3, and 4, Central tendency and data variation are described by mean and standard deviation. The correlation in which the relationship of two variables is quantified was used in problem 5. In the context of problem 6, several regression analysis was performed in order to consider one variable as a dependent and others as independent. In problem 7, the relationships between the concepts that explain the phenomenon under study were modeled using causal relations.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Knowledge of Triage System Among Nurses on Quality Healthcare Delivery; Understanding | n=260*

Statement	M	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. Triage is the sorting of patients into priority of injuries or illness.	4.69	.633	Strongly Agree	Very High Knowledge
2. The purpose of triage is to prevent deterioration or death of a patient while waiting on the queue for his/her turn.	4.56	.776	Strongly Agree	Very High Knowledge
3. Triage is to identify patients needing immediate resuscitation	4.59	.732	Strongly Agree	Very High Knowledge
4. Triage is the process of rapidly examining sick children when they first arrive to place them in one of the following categories: Those with EMERGENCY SIGNS who require immediate emergency treatment.	4.60	.692	Strongly Agree	Very High Knowledge
5. Triage is difficult and costly to implement in district emergency units.	3.83	1.087	Agree	High Knowledge
Overall Mean	4.45	.571	Agree	High Knowledge

Based on the severity of the injury, triage assigns a higher priority to patient care to help most people recover as much as possible in the least amount of time.

The triage knowledge and skills of emergency nurses along with other relevant criteria must be examined. Triage is allocating the appropriate resources to meet the patient's medical needs and putting the patient in the right place at the right time to receive the proper degree of care. The caregiver can be assigned to a suitable assessment and treatment site because to this hospital's location.

As shown in Table 1, the participants rated their Level of Knowledge of the Triage System Among Nurses on Quality Healthcare Delivery, specifically Understanding of nurses about the triage system, which got an overall mean of 4.45, and this was verbally described as High Knowledge of the understanding of triage system, it means that when nurses exhibit a complete understanding of the characteristics of triage system in the hospital and show mindfulness which includes being knowledgeable that based on the severity of the injury, triage assigns a higher priority to patient care intending to help most people recover as much as possible in the least amount of time, and the process of rapidly examining sick children when they first arrive to place them in one of the following categories that those with emergency time who require immediate emergency treatment.

These can be supported through the following studies such as: The research published by Duko et al., 2019 indicates that nurses exhibit a commendable level of triage abilities albeit some further training on their triage knowledge is still required. They also recognized correlations between working experience, educational level, triage experience with triage knowledge. The efficiency of the triage system is largely dependent on the expertise and clinical abilities of the personnel designated for this task, with the nurses being crucial in the patients' needs categorization. (AlShatarat, Rayan, Eshah, Baqees, Jaber, & AlBashtawy, 2022). If triage is done without due skills and knowledge, the patients are misclassified (Vatnøy, Fossum, Smith, & Slettebø, 2013). In other words, the effectiveness of triage systems lies in the professional knowledge and clinical skills of the triage staff, including nurses. (Phukubye, Mbombi, & Mothiba, 2019).

Table 2. *Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Knowledge of the Triage System Among Nurses on Quality Healthcare Delivery; Clinical Judgment | n=260*

Statement	M	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. On a patient's arrival, I can decide if the patient needs immediate care based on a first look.	3.99	.913	Agree	High Knowledge
2. I can intuitively identify a patient experiencing cardiac arrest.	4.01	.881	Agree	High Knowledge
3. I can interpret a patient's symptoms by considering his/her underlying diseases.	3.88	.816	Agree	High Knowledge
4. I can identify several diseases based on a patient's complaints.	3.94	.761	Agree	High Knowledge
5. I know which severe symptoms should be addressed with priority.	4.28	.678	Agree	High Knowledge
Overall Mean	4.02	.596	Agree	High Knowledge

Table 2 illustrates the participants assessing their Level of Knowledge of Triage System Among Nurses on Quality Healthcare Delivery specifically, Clinical Judgment which got an overall mean of 4.02 (SD=0.596), and which is verbally described as High Knowledge. This means that nurses exhibit a fully intuitive identification of patient status that shows symptoms should be addressed in the sorting of patients as to priority of injuries or illness. This process of rapidly examining sick individuals when they first arrive serves to help decide where to place them in one of the following categories such as those who require immediate emergency treatment.

Among the statements on Knowledge of Triage systems among Nurses on Quality Healthcare Delivery, they rated the dimension, statement 5 as "I know which severe symptoms should be addressed with priority," got the highest mean of 4.28 (SD = 0.678), followed by statement 2, "I can intuitively identify a patient experiencing cardiac arrest," of 4.01 (SD = 0.881), respectively, with the spread of responses variation of the nurses in the triage system.

As it appears in the research undertaken by Callihan et al. in 2022, it was discovered that emergency nurses regardless of their long service or several years of experience exhibited a deficiency in clinical judgment skills. It is important to comprehend the factors that encourage clinical judgment in the emergency departments to ensure patient safety and quality care.

Aghabarary et al. (2023) concluded that emergency nurses exhibit moderate levels of clinical judgment. Clinical judgment is an important aspect in facilities with complex emergency departments architectures; however, substantial workloads can hinder the practice. Nurses may be more concerned with the accomplishment of tasks for instance, as opposed to clinical judgment, which may result in dangers to patients. It is therefore imperative that the clinical judgment of emergency nurses is improved for the benefit and safety of patients. (Noon, 2014)

Schubert et al. (2013) conducted research and analyzed the characteristics of novice and expert nurses in terms of their clinical judgment skills should facilitate training program designs in such areas which have high levels of complex functions. In addition, triage nurses must be able to determine whether they face a static or dynamic situation when generating their judgment into a decision (Noon, 2014).

Table 3. *Descriptive Statistics on the Level of Knowledge of Triage System Among Nurses on Quality Healthcare Delivery; Expert Assessment | n=260*

Statement	M	SD	Verbal	
			Description	Interpretation
1. During an interview with the patient for triage I can investigate the patient by scanning him/her from head to toe.	4.11	.764	Agree	High Knowledge
2. Based on a patient's complaints, I can identify if the patient needs to be isolated for a suspected infectious disease.	4.10	.815	Agree	High Knowledge
3. I can perform a simple assessment to confirm the disease I suspect.	3.96	.842	Agree	High Knowledge
Overall Mean	4.06	.659	Agree	High Knowledge

As shown in Table 3, the participants rated their Level of Knowledge of the Triage System Among Nurses on Quality Healthcare Delivery, specifically Expert Assessment, which got an overall mean of 4.06 (SD = 0.659), and this was verbally described as High Knowledge on the expert assessment of the triage system, which means that when a nurse exhibits full attention during an interview with the patient for triage and investigates the patient by scanning based on a patient's complaints, it also identifies if the patient needs to be isolated for a suspected infectious disease with priority in the sorting of patients into priority of injuries or illness and the process of rapidly examining sick individuals when they first arrive to place them in one of the following categories: those with emergency time who require immediate emergency treatment.

Among the statements on Knowledge of Triage System Among Nurses on Quality Healthcare Delivery, as they rated the dimension, statement 1, "During an interview with the patient for triage, I can investigate the patient by scanning him/her from head to toe," got the highest mean of 4.11 (SD = 0.764), with the spread of responses variation of the nurses in the triage system.

Callihan et al. (2022) discovered that the evaluations of triage nurses for the same case are subjective even when the final diagnosis is known. A trained person may detect unsafe triage without knowing the clinical outcome but may be inconsistent with other assessors. The study advocates that an expert's evaluation of a series of cases is likely to give a better picture of the safety and quality of triage than a case-by-case evaluation.

Knowledge of triage assessment for nurses is the key element of supervision in ED. Triage nurses should have knowledge regarding triage assessment, level of category, and skills for triage. The triage system assesses and prioritizes patients based on severity level. To enhance the triage skills and knowledge of nurses, continuing education and training courses related to triage assessment and advanced management of medical emergencies are key aspects in order to increase the quality of care and patient safety (Ali et al., 2013).

The research by Ariffin et al. (2023) throws light on the significant role of evaluation and training on a regular basis in ensuring that the triage system stays relevant and accurate. Through training and evaluation, organizations can maintain a conducive and safe environment for patients and reduce the chances of aggression.

Conclusions

The study concludes that nurses possess advanced knowledge and comprehension of triage systems, especially their ability to rank patients according to the degree of injuries or illnesses and assess the patients accurately. The results indicate that the ability of the nurses would give them the capacity to make full use of the triage systems without challenges while promoting effective healthcare.

This research proposes various measures to enhance the triage practices within emergency units. There should be a training refresher program for nurses on the triage protocols, while a centralized admissions office would facilitate patient registrations. There can be training on triage that incorporate various experiences of the nurses in that specific unit. Coupling novice nurses with senior nurses can also aid in decision making. Nurses need to play their roles as caregivers, nurses performing triage duties, and educators effectively. Other studies can employ other variables as well and create a study on the triage practices and their effects on the health care systems.

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